

Supplementary information

Table S1: Summary of the log-logistic model parameters (b , e) fitted to *Trissolcus japonicus* mortality data using LL.4() function in *drc* package (available at <https://cran.r-project.org/package=drc>). Lower limit parameter (c), corresponding to acetone only, was fixed at 0 (as no mortality was observed), while upper limit parameter (d), corresponding to 100% of insecticide field dose, was fixed at 1 (as all parasitoids died with the maximum concentration tested).

parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	t-value	P
b	-1.17359	0.11984	-9.7933	< 0.0001
e	2.91713	0.41362	7.0527	< 0.0001

Table S2: Details and statistical comparisons of the different linear models tested in backward model selection for evaluating the effect of different treatments on the residence time of *T. japonicus* in the contaminated area of the open arena (Experiment 1). The best-fit model is highlighted in bold.

Explanatory variables	AIC	Model comparison
Model 1) Insecticide, conditioning, host traces, and three-way interaction	1878.9	vs. best model: $F = 0.275$, $df = 4$, $P = 0.89$
Model 2) Insecticide, conditioning, host traces, and all the two-way interactions	1877.0	vs. best model: $F = 0.321$, $df = 3$, $P = 0.81$
Model 3) Insecticide, conditioning, host traces	1872.0	vs. null model: $F = 62.44$, $df = 3$, $P < 0.0001$

Table S3: Details and statistical comparisons of the different generalised linear models (quasi-Poisson distribution) tested in backward model selection for evaluating the effect of different treatments on the number of visits of *T. japonicus* in the contaminated area of the open arena (Experiment 1). The best-fit model is highlighted in bold.

Explanatory variables	qAIC	Model comparison
Model 1) Insecticide, conditioning, host traces, and three-way interaction	889.9	vs. best model: Dev. diff. = 4.496, P = 0.89
Model 2) Insecticide, conditioning, host traces, and all the two-way interactions	890.5	vs. best model: Dev. diff. = 4.450, P = 0.79
Model 3) Insecticide, conditioning, host traces	891.1	vs. best model: Dev. diff. = 3.136, P = 0.27
Model 4) Conditioning, host traces	882.9	vs. null model: Dev. Diff. = 75.474, P < 0.0001

Table S4: Summary of the hypotheses tested within the best-fit linear model on the residence time of *Trissolcus japonicus* in the contaminated area of the open arena (Experiment 1). The response variable was Box-Cox transformed before the analysis. For each comparison, the estimated mean difference (on transformed scale), SE, t-value, df, and P-value are reported.

Planned comparisons	Estimate	SE	t	df	P
Insecticide: neonic vs control	0.41	0.15	2.76	486	0.006
Conditioning: naïve vs conditioned	1.92	0.15	13.04	486	< 0.0001
Host traces: <i>Halyomorpha halys</i> vs <i>Arma custos</i>	0.50	0.15	3.37	486	0.0008

Table S5: Summary of the hypotheses tested within the best-fit model on the number of visits of *Trissolcus japonicus* in the contaminated area of the open arena (Experiment 1). For each comparison, the estimated mean difference, SE, z, and P-value are reported.

Planned comparisons	Estimate	SE	z	P
Conditioning: naïve vs conditioned	0.30	0.08	3.58	0.0004
Host traces: <i>Halyomorpha halys</i> vs <i>Arma custos</i>	0.33	0.08	4.00	< 0.0001

Table S6: Details and statistical comparisons of the different linear models tested in backward model selection for evaluating the effect of different treatments on linear speed, tortuosity, and activity of *Trissolcus japonicus* in the contaminated area of the closed arena (Experiment 3). The best-fit model is highlighted in bold.

Response variable	Explanatory variables	AIC	Model comparison
Linear speed	Model 1) Insecticide, host traces, and two-way interaction	457.9	vs. best model: F = 0.020, df = 1, P = 0.89
	Model 2) Insecticide, host traces	455.9	vs. null model: F = 19.369, df = 2, P < 0.0001
Tortuosity	Model 1) Insecticide, host traces, and two-way interaction	-64.4	vs. best model: F = 0.527, df = 1, P = 0.47
	Model 2) Insecticide, host traces	-65.9	vs. null model: F = 16.988, df = 2, P < 0.0001
Activity	Model 1) Insecticide, host traces, and two-way interaction	-263.6	vs. null model: F = 35.781, df = 3, P = 0.003

Table S7: Summary of the hypotheses tested within the best-fit linear models selected in Table S6 (Experiment 3). Response variables were Box-Cox transformed (linear speed) or arcsine transformed (tortuosity and activity) before the analysis. For each comparison, the estimated mean difference (on transformed scale), SE, t-value, df, and P-value are reported.

Response variable	Planned comparisons	Estimate	SE	t	df	P
Linear speed	Host traces: Hh traces vs no traces	-27.000	5.360	-5.048	57	< 0.0001
	Insecticide: neonic vs control	19.500	5.360	3.640	57	0.0006
Tortuosity	Host traces: Hh traces vs no traces	0.288	0.069	4.153	57	0.0001
	Insecticide: neonic vs control	-0.283	0.069	-4.090	57	0.0001
Activity	Host traces (control): Hh traces vs no traces	-0.004	0.009	-0.424	56	0.67
	Host traces (neonic): Hh traces vs no traces	-0.045	0.009	-4.812	56	< 0.0001
	Insecticide (without traces): neonic vs control	-0.040	0.009	-4.287	56	0.0001
	Insecticide (with traces): neonic vs control	-0.081	0.009	-8.675	56	< 0.0001